

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO THE USAGE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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Abstract. *The article discusses methodological approaches to the use of phraseological units in English lessons in primary, secondary and high schools. The main attention is paid to the specifics of teaching using phraseological units at different stages of training.*

Keywords: *phraseological units, English language, students, skills.*

Phraseology is the golden fund of language and culture. Phraseological units convey a unique flavor that distinguishes languages from each other. They enrich speech not only quantitatively, but also qualitatively, since they are able to clearly and figuratively express the essence of quite complex phenomena, however, such speech units can represent a trap for those who study a foreign language. The danger lies in the fact that existing phraseological units, understandable to native speakers, not only may not be recorded in dictionaries, but may also combine the possibilities of dual use of both bound and free units. That is why it is very important to teach students to recognize phraseological units in the text and find the correct translation solution.

Avoiding the nuances of translating phraseological units can lead to mistakes and loss of the image, and often even the meaning of the text.

As noted by T.A. Kazakov, the main feature of phraseological units, according to many modern researchers, is the partial or complete discrepancy between the plan of content and the plan of expression, which determines the specificity of the phraseological unit [1; 127], and which, of course, will influence the choice of techniques and methods of their translation.

“The optimal translating solution when translating phraseological units is to search for an identical phraseological unit in the target language. It should be taken into account that the number of such direct correspondences between Uzbek and English is very limited. If there are no direct matches, then the original phraseological unit can be translated by searching for a similar phraseological unit, which has a common original meaning, but is built on a different verbal basis. It should be taken into account that phraseological units that are often similar in meaning but different in form in different languages have different emotional and associative connotations and are not always interchangeable” [1; 140].

If there are no identical or similar phraseological units in the Uzbek language, and they cannot be translated literally, a translation-explanation of the figurative meaning of the phraseological unit is used for this, that is, by turning a stable phrase into a free one. With such a translation, phraseological units are deprived their figurative and associative properties. An acceptable method for translating phraseological units, although less effective, is tracing. The study of English phraseology at school occurs at all stages: primary, middle and high school. It is the internal connection between these stages that ensures students’ successful mastery of the topic. This topic is used at each stage to expand vocabulary. However, it must be remembered that everyone the learning stage carries various goals, methods and techniques of teaching.

At the primary school stage, it is best to use game activities with cards and creative mini-projects. The topic of translating phraseological units containing an element of natural phenomena in their semantics can be easily connected with the topics of the school curriculum “Weather” and

“Seasons”. Knowing such phraseological units, children will be able to immerse themselves in playful activities and happily study two topics at the same time. Linguistic scientists have proven that phraseological units are firmly embedded in memory, the memorization process is facilitated by various consonances, rhymes, and rhythms. Phraseologisms are also used to introduce a new phonetic phenomenon, perform exercises to consolidate new phonetic material and repeat it during phonetic exercises.

In the middle classes, when using phraseological units in an English lesson, students improve their auditory-pronunciation and rhythmic-intonation skills. Firstly, pronunciation skills are automated, and secondly, students learn to divide sentences into syntagms and determine logical stress. The topic of translating phraseological units that contain an element of natural phenomena in their semantics can already be connected with the more voluminous topics of the school curriculum “Holidays”, “Weather” and “Clothing”. In the middle grades, more complex examples of idioms may be introduced. At this stage, it is worth introducing students to new material about the types of translation of phraseological units and its distinctive features. Students are introduced to dialogic speech, essays in English, and a set of independent exercises.

In high school, phraseological units are used in teaching grammar and regional studies. Phraseologisms become a tool for expressing thoughts and contribute to the automation and activation of grammatical forms and structures. It is worth paying attention to the features of the translation of phraseological units that contain an element of natural phenomena in their semantics when studying more serious topics in the school curriculum, for example, “Adolescent Problems,” “Politics,” “Tolerance,” “Media” and others. At this stage, students can independently analyze phraseological units, translate them correctly, taking into account all the specifics, also find their origin, and correctly explain the meaning of idioms. The ability to correctly apply phraseological units in dialogic speech and construct competent, emotionally expressive sentences is the responsibility of a middle school student.

It should be noted that phraseological units are perfect as phonetic exercises at the beginning of a lesson, when introducing new phonetic material and repeating it, as well as for developing students' monologue speech as a problem situation and reasoning about the meaning of a particular proverb. The obvious benefit of introducing phraseological units is also evident when teaching pronunciation, as well as when creating difficult to pronounce sounds. Yu.A. correctly notes. Dementenko, on the one hand, pronunciation skills are automated, and on the other, students learn to divide sentences into syntagms, determine logical stress, etc. Therefore, the use of phraseological units in teaching pronunciation is extremely appropriate and effective [3; 1]. Phraseological units are indispensable when teaching the grammatical side of speech. The ability to correctly combine words and change phrases depending on the communicative situation is one of the most important conditions for using language as a means of communication. Most often in speech, phraseological units perform an incentive function, i.e. help in communicative situations to express: wishes, requests, advice, warnings, permission.

Learning new phraseological units helps enrich students' vocabulary. At the same time, teachers can focus on the grammatical aspect that is relevant specifically for this lesson, compiling your own selection of phraseological units. For example, when studying verbs (to think someone hung the moon - kimnidir mukammal deb hisoblash, persuade someone that the moon is made of green cheese - kimgadir ochiq-oydin bema'niligini isbotlash, reach for the moon - aql bovar qilmaydigan cho'qqilarni zabt etishga intilish, osmonlarga yetishga harakat qilish), articles (to ask/cry for the moon - imkonsiz narsani talab qilish, once in a blue moon - kamdan kam, in the

eye of the storm - voqealar markazida bo'lmoq), comparative constructions (feel right as rain - o'zini ajoyib his etmoq, welcome as snow in harvest - biror kishining kelganini yoqtirmaslik, pure as the driven snow - birinchi qordek pokiza va beg'ubor), etc.

Thus, the study of phraseological units contributes to a better understanding by students of English-speaking culture, the mentality of the English people, as well as the development of linguistic and regional competence.

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